

PERFORMANCE OF MODELS FOR PREDICTING THE SHEAR CAPACITY OF FRP-STRENGTHENED RC BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

The behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) beams shear strengthened with fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) has been extensively studied. Numerous analytical models have been proposed to predict the shear contribution of externally applied FRP to RC beams. Due to the continuous increase of experimental data, it is fundamental to assess the predictive performance of these models, to find the most appropriate ones and their boundaries of application. This study evaluates the predictive performance of some available models using a comprehensive database of published works. The results reveal that current models have significant shortcomings, resulting in unreliable and potentially unsafe predictions. Therefore, a new simple and more effective model is required. This preliminary study briefly discusses potential approaches to improve the accuracy of these models.

KEYWORDS

Shear strengthening; Externally bonded reinforcement; Empirical prediction models.

INTRODUCTION

FRP has been used extensively in the past three decades to increase the shear resistance of RC beams, but modelling its contribution with high accuracy is still a challenge due to the involved complex phenomena. Most design guidelines use a conventional truss model to simplify the shear contribution of FRP reinforcement. Unlike steel reinforcement, whose contribution at ultimate limit state (ULS) conditions can be full mobilized (yield stress), a concept of effective strain (ε_{fe}) should be used for evaluating the FRP shear contribution since it generally debonds prematurely (before attaining its ultimate tensile strain). Experimental evidence (Mofidi & Chaallal, 2011; Oller et al., 2021) shows the ε_{fe} depends on several parameters, such as the FRP stiffness, quality of concrete substrate, strengthening configuration, bond length, and reinforcement ratio of existing shear reinforcement (stirrups). The existing models have different approaches for estimating ε_{fe} , but it is fundamental to assess the reliability of these estimates, taking the advantage of the available experimental results with RC beams FRP-shear strengthened according to the externally bonded reinforcement (EBR) technique.

A sizable dataset consisting of 344 experimental outcomes of EBR-reinforced beams subjected to shear strengthening was compiled. The tested models in this study are those the authors assumed as the more commonly used by academics and designers, namely: (fib-Bulletin90, 2019), (CNR-DT200R1/2013, 2013), (EN1998-3, 2005), (ACI440.2R-17, 2017), (TR55, 2012), (CIDAR, 2006), and (Chen et al., 2013). The formulation of these models is resumed in the appendix. The predictive performance of each model was evaluated using this database and by model uncertainty metrics, and other statistical indicators of accuracy. Then, the study analysed existing models and found that they did not account for the interaction between externally bonded FRP reinforcement and internal transverse shear reinforcement, which was shown to be crucial. These results highlight the importance of considering this interaction in the behaviour of RC beams strengthened with FRP. In addition, a demerit classification was established for each model in order to find the most reliable one. Since certain guidelines/models do not provide equations for side-bonded strengthening configuration, the present study concentrates solely on beams that have been reinforced using either fully wrapped or U-wrapped configurations. Furthermore, results from strengthening configurations using anchorage systems to avoid premature debonding of the FRP were also not considered.

DATA COLLECTION, SCREENING, AND OUTLIER DETECTION

An already existing database (Barros et al., 2011) was screened, resulting 344 tested RC beams shear strengthened with externally bonded FRP reinforcements including information regarding the geometry, material properties, FRP and conventional steel reinforcement details, and test results. The dataset was filtered to exclude specimens with one or more of the following characteristics: (1) specimens with missing data required for analysis; (2) specimens that did not use carbon fibres for reinforcement; (3) specimens reinforced using the NSM technique; (4) specimens with negligible shear contribution from FRP, which suggested potential issues with the strengthening process; (5) specimens with side-bonded FRP reinforcement, since this technique is not considered in certain guidelines (such as in fib bulletin 90); (6) specimens that were strengthened with FRP systems with multidirectional fibres; and (7) specimens with any type of end anchorage as their effectiveness is too dependent on the specific type of anchorage used.

Outliers were also eliminated from the database, by using the Mahalanobis Distance (MD) Method, since it has been demonstrated an effective approach for database with multivariate data, such is the case (Todeschini et al., 2013).

STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTIC OF THE VARIABLES

The statistical characteristics of the 344 experimental data are indicated in Table 1. The frequency distributions and boxplots of five variables (which are the combination of eight other input variables) beside the ratio of shear contribution of FRP to total shear resistance of these specimens are shown in Figure 1. The dispersion of data indicates that the analysis incorporated a broad spectrum of input variables to examine the influence of important input variables on the contribution of FRP.

Table 1: Statistical characteristics of design variables of the strengthened beam

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	Q ₁ ¹	Median	Q ₃ ²	SD ³	CoV ⁴
Average concrete compressive strength, f_{cm} (MPa)	10.6	61.3	33.7	27.4	32.8	38	10.1	0.3
Natural logarithm of axial stiffness of FRP $\ln(E_f t_f)$ in (N / mm)	9.53	13.5	10.74	10.2	10.6	11.2	0.66	0.06
FRP to beam's web depth ratio, h_f / h_w	0.61	1.0	0.91	0.79	1.0	1.0	0.12	0.13
Stirrup ratio ρ_{sw} (%)	0	0.0142	0.0016	0	0.0011	0.0026	0.0019	1.18
Shear span to effective depth ratio, a/d	1.14	5.0	2.76	2.45	2.90	3.11	0.67	0.24
FRP shear contribution to total shear resistance V_f / V_R (%)	3.9	71.9	31.7	20.1	29.9	43.6	15.0	0.47

¹SD: standard deviation, ²Q₁: lower quartile, ³Q₃: upper quartile, ⁴CoV: Coefficient of variation

Figure 1: The frequency distributions and boxplots of some important input features of the database and the ratio of shear contribution of FRP in comparison with the total shear resistance.

VALIDATION AND COMPARISON

The performance of existing selected models was evaluated by comparing their predictions in terms of the nominal FRP shear contribution to the experimental values, which were determined from:

$$V_{R,f}^{\text{exp}} = V_R^{\text{str}} - V_R^{\text{ref}} \quad (1)$$

where V_R^{ref} and V_R^{str} is the shear resistance of the reference and strengthened beam, respectively.

A summary of the existing considered models to obtain the nominal shear contribution of FRP ($V_{R,f}^{\text{model}}$) is given in the appendix. For the material properties used in these formulations, average values were used, and partial factors are set equal to 1.0. The inclination of the shear crack is assumed to be 45° , and a corner radius of 20 mm is assumed, when not provided. To evaluate the predictive accuracy of existing considered models, the model error is calculated as the experimental to the predicted ratio:

$$\chi = \frac{V_{R,f}^{\text{exp}}}{V_{R,f}^{\text{model}}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 displays the performance of the models, with two columns of plots for each model. The first plot shows the scatter of model predictions *versus* experimentally determined values. The mean, median, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation of χ are also depicted in this graph. The second plot shows the boxplot of χ for continuous and discrete FRP configurations. Figure 3 reports the mean, standard deviation, median, and coefficient of variation (CoV) of the model error for all the above-described existing models.

It is verified that all the considered models generally produced overestimated and dispersed predictions (having a median of model errors below one, and a large value of CoV). Nevertheless, (CIDAR, 2006) stands out among all other models, with a median model error of 1.02 and the lowest coefficient of variation (0.57). The considered models are generally biased and produce unconservative predictions for both fully wrapped and U-wrapped beams. They also particularly produce more unconservative predictions for beams strengthened with continuous FRP sheets. However, (CIDAR, 2006) shows less unconservative predictions for beams strengthened with continuous FRP sheets.

Figure 2: $V_{R,f}^{model}$ versus $V_{R,f}^{exp}$, boxplot of χ for continuous and discrete configuration. a) fib bulletin 90, b) CNR, c) ACI, d) CIDAR, e) TR55, f) Chen, g) EN 1998-3.

Figure 3: Statistical indicators of χ for the analysed models.

All above-mentioned existing models, with the exception of the one introduced by Chen et al's (2013) do not consider the influence of the interaction between internal steel stirrups and externally bonded FRP reinforcement on the beam's shear capacity. It should be noted that Chen et al's model considers certain stirrup properties that are not readily available in the literature. Figure 4 exhibits a 3D scatterplot of the model errors based on the steel ratio ($A_{sw}/b_w s_s$) and equivalent FRP ratio ($(E_f/E_s)A_{fwe}/b_w s_f$).

The mean of the model errors projected onto each plane of this 3D plot is depicted by two red lines. The p-values are computed and displayed, using a significance level of 0.05, to help decide whether to reject or accept the null hypothesis of unbiased estimates. If the p-value is less than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is evidence to suggest that the estimates are biased. On the other hand, if the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, then the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no evidence to suggest that the estimates are biased. Upon observing the figure and the reported p-values for each model, it can be inferred that all existing models are deficient in producing unbiased predictions regarding steel ratio and equivalent FRP ratio. Specifically, in beams strengthened with high steel and/or equivalent FRP ratio, these models tend to overestimate the results. This discrepancy arises due to the models' inability to account for the failure mechanism at higher ratios of steel and FRP reinforcement ratio. It is noteworthy that based on the p-values reported, CIDAR indicates lower level of bias in comparison with other models.

A classification system based solely on descriptive statistics of model error may not provide sufficient information to assess the reliability of a design proposal in terms of structural reliability. This is because a model error of 0.5 is worse than a model error of 2, which is not accounted for in the previous statistical analysis (Barros et al., 2007). To address this issue, a Demerit Point Scale Methodology is used, which assigns a penalty point to each range of model error. The total demerit point score is calculated by multiplying the percentage of model error in each range by the corresponding demerit point, and then summing the products. This score ranges between 0 and 10, with a smaller score indicating better model performance. Table 2 provides the range of model error, their penalties, and the percentage of specimens falling within each range. The overall model performance is evaluated by a cumulative penalty score. Based on the values in Table 2, CIDAR is deemed to produce more reliable predictions as it exhibits the least demerit points.

Table 2. Demerit point classification.

χ	Classification	Penalty	fib bulletin 90	CNR	ACI	CIDAR	TR55	Chen	EN
<0.5	Extremely dangerous	10	31 ^a	27	21	15	18	17	30
0.5-0.65	Dangerous	5	15	13	14	11	13	14	12
0.65-0.85	Low safety	2	10	11	16	13	18	15	12
0.85-1.3	Appropriate safety	0	17	17	17	28	18	22	14
1.3-2	Conservative	1	17	16	19	23	17	19	12
>2	Extremely conservative	2	10	15	14	10	17	12	20
Total demerit point score			4.42	4.03	3.59	2.74 ^b	3.32	3.13	4.36

a: Percentage of specimens with χ laying in the range, b: $((15 \times 10) + (11 \times 5) + (13 \times 2) + (28 \times 0) + (23 \times 1) + (10 \times 2)) / 100 = 2.74$

Figure 4: Model errors versus steel-FRP interaction factor, a) fib bulletin 90, b)CNR, c)ACI, d) CIDAR, e) TR55, f)Chen, g) EN 1998-3.

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the performance of some of the most used models for determining the shear resistance of RC beams strengthened with externally bonded FRP reinforcement. The considered models were *fib*-bulletin 90, CNR-DT 200, ACI 440.2R-17, CIDAR, TR 55, EN 1998-3, and Chen et al.'s model. To conduct this analysis, a comprehensive database of 344 RC beams was compiled from literature. The scope of this study was limited to FRP systems applied according to full wrapping and U-wrapping strengthening configurations. In the models' prediction, average values were considered for the material properties and unit values were adopted for the safety factors. From the studies carried out, the following conclusions can be extracted:

- 1- Among the existing models, CIDAR exhibits the lowest degree of model error dispersion with a coefficient of variation of 0.57. Additionally, with a median model error of approximately one, CIDAR offers the most well-balanced predictions in terms of unsafe and conservative predictions.
- 2- The predictions of the models were unexpectedly unconservative when applied to RC beams that were strengthened using continuous arrangements of FRP reinforcement. However, in comparison to other prediction models, CIDAR displayed superior performance when dealing with this type of beams.
- 3- All models fail to produce unbiased prediction in relation with internal steel stirrups and externally bonded FRP reinforcement. This omission has led to more overestimated predictions for RC beams with a high value of steel ratio or FRP reinforcement ratio. Nonetheless, CIDAR demonstrated the best performance also in this aspect.
- 4- Based on the reliability analysis conducted in this study, CIDAR produces the most reliable predictions when compared to the other considered models, while *fib* bulletin 90 exhibits the least reliable predictions. It must be noted that high percentage of dangerous and extremely dangerous predictions underscores the urgent need for a more reliable model.
- 5- For future research, the authors intend to utilize the current database to develop a more reliable model, including the application of machine learning algorithms.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX: Formulation of the considered models

Models	Formulation
fib-bulletin 90	$V_{Rd,f} = A_{fwc} h_{fe} f_{fwd} (\cot \theta + \cot \alpha) \sin \alpha$ $A_{fw} = 2w_f t_f \quad t_f = \begin{cases} t_0 n_f & \text{if } n_f < 4 \\ t_0 n_f^{0.85} & \text{if } n_f \geq 4 \end{cases}; A_{fwc} = \begin{cases} \frac{A_{fw}}{s_f} & \text{if strips of FRP} \\ 2t_f \sin \alpha & \text{if continuous FRP} \end{cases}$ $h_{fe} = \min(h_f, h - 0.1d) \quad t_0 : \text{Thickness of each layer}$ <p>Fully wrapped: $f_{fwd} = f_{fwd,c} = a_t k_R \cdot f_{fd}; a_t = 0.8; f_{fd} = \frac{f_{fu}}{\gamma_f}$</p> $k_R = \begin{cases} 0.5 \frac{R}{50} \left(2 - \frac{R}{50} \right) & R < 50 \text{ mm} \\ 0.5 & R \geq 50 \text{ mm} \end{cases}$ <p>U-shaped: $f_{fwd} = \min f_{fbwd}, f_{fwd,c}$ for continuous FRP sheets:</p> $a) f_{fbwd} = \left[1 - \frac{1}{3} \frac{l_e}{h_{fe} / \sin \alpha} \right] \frac{f_{fbk}}{\gamma_{fb}} \quad \text{for } x \geq l_e$ $b) f_{fbwd} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{h_{fe} / \sin \alpha}{l_e} \frac{f_{fbk}}{\gamma_{fb}} \quad \text{for } x \leq l_e$ <p>for discrete FRP sheets:</p> $a) f_{fbwd} = \frac{f_{fbk}}{\gamma_{fb}} \quad \text{for } x \geq l_e; \text{ and } l_e \leq y \leq x$ $b) f_{fbwd} = \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{2}{3} \frac{ms_f}{l_e} \right) \frac{m}{n} \right] \frac{f_{fbk}}{\gamma_{fb}} \quad \text{for } x \geq l_e; \text{ and } y \leq l_e$ $c) f_{fbwd} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{ns_f}{l_e} \frac{f_{fbk}}{\gamma_{fb}} \quad \text{for } x \leq l_e; \text{ and } y \leq x$ $x = h_{fe} / \sin \alpha \quad l_e = \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{E_f t_f s_{0k}}{\tau_{b1k}}}$ $y = s_f / \cot \theta + \cot \alpha \sin \alpha \quad \tau_{b1k} = 0.44 \sqrt{f_{cm} f_{ctm}}$ $n = \text{int} \left[\frac{h_{fe} \cot \theta + \cot \alpha}{s_f} \right] \quad s_{0k} = 0.23$ $m = \text{int} \left[\frac{l_e \cot \theta + \cot \alpha \sin \alpha}{s_f} \right] \quad f_{fbk} = \sqrt{\frac{E_f s_{0k} \tau_{b1k}}{t_f}}$
CNR-DT 200 R1/2013	$V_{R,f} = \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd}} 0.9d \cdot f_{fe} \cdot 2t_f (\cot \theta + \cot \alpha) \frac{w_f}{s_f \sin \alpha}$ <p>U-Wrapped: $f_{fe} = f_{fd} \left[1 - \frac{1}{3} \frac{l_{ed} \sin \alpha}{\min(0.9d, h_w)} \right]$ Fully wrapped: $f_{fe} = f_{fd} \left[1 - \frac{1}{6} \frac{l_{ed} \sin \alpha}{\min(0.9d, h_w)} \right] + \max \left(0, \left(\frac{1}{2} \kappa_R f_{fd} - f_{dd} \left[1 - \frac{l_{ed} \sin \alpha}{\min(0.9d, h_w)} \right] \right) \right)$</p> $\kappa_R = 0.2 + 1.6 \frac{R}{b_w}, \text{ with } 0 \leq \frac{R}{b_w} \leq 0.5 \quad f_{fd} = \frac{1}{\gamma_{fd}} \sqrt{\frac{2E_f \Gamma_{fd}}{t_f}}, \Gamma_{fd} = \frac{k_b k_G}{FC} \sqrt{f_{cm} f_{ctm}}$ $k_b = \sqrt{\frac{2 - w_f / s_f \sin \alpha}{1 + w_f / s_f \sin \alpha}} \geq 1 \quad \text{if } w_f / b < 0.25, k_b \text{ is equal to } 1.18; k_G = \begin{cases} 0.037 & \text{Wet lay-up} \\ 0.023 & \text{pre-cured} \end{cases}$ <p>For continuous sheets:</p> $w_f = \min(0.9d, h_w) \frac{\sin(\theta + \alpha)}{\sin \theta}, \quad s_f = w_f / \sin \alpha$ $l_{ed} = \max \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd} f_{bd}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 E_f t_f \Gamma_{Fd}}{2}}, 200 \text{ mm} \right), \quad f_{bd} = \frac{2\Gamma_{Fd}}{s_u}, \quad s_u = 0.25 \text{ mm}$
ACI 440.2R-17	$V_{R,f} = \phi \cdot \psi_f \left(\frac{A_{fv} f_{fe} d_{fv} (\sin \alpha + \cos \alpha)}{s_f} \right), \quad A_{fv} = 2t_f w_f$ $f_{fe} = E_f \varepsilon_{fe}$

EN 1998-3	<p>Fully wrapped: $\varepsilon_{fe} = 0.004 \leq 0.75\varepsilon_{fu}$</p> <p>U wrapped: $\varepsilon_{fe} = \kappa_v \varepsilon_{fu} \leq 0.004, \kappa_v = \frac{\kappa_1 \kappa_2 L_e}{11900 \cdot \varepsilon_f} \leq 0.75,$</p> $L_e = \frac{23300}{(t_f E_f)^{0.58}}, \kappa_1 = \left(\frac{f'_c}{27} \right)^{2/3}, \kappa_2 = \frac{d_{fv} - L_e}{d_{fv}}$
EN 1998-3	<p>$V_{R,f} = 0.9d \cdot f_{fe} \cdot 2t_f \left(\frac{w_f}{s_f} \right)^2 (\cot \theta + \cot \alpha) \sin \alpha$</p> <p>U-Wrapped: $f_{fe} = f_{fd} \left[1 - \frac{\pi - 2}{\pi} \frac{L_e \sin \alpha}{0.9d} \right]$</p> <p>Fully wrapped: $f_{fe} = f_{fd} \left[1 - \frac{\pi - 2}{2\pi} \frac{L_e \sin \alpha}{0.9d} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ 0, \langle \kappa_R \cdot f_{fu} - f_{fd} \rangle \left[1 - \frac{L_e \sin \alpha}{0.9d} \right] \right\}$</p> $L_e = \sqrt{\frac{E_f t_f}{7.2 f_{ctm} \kappa_b}}$ $f_{fd} = \frac{1}{\gamma_{fd}} \sqrt{\frac{0.6 E_f f_{ctm} \kappa_b}{t_f}}, \kappa_R = 0.2 + 1.6 \frac{R}{b_w}, \text{ with } 0 \leq \frac{R}{b_w} \leq 0.5$ $\kappa_b = \sqrt{1.5 \left(2 - \frac{w_f}{s_f} \right) / \left(1 + \frac{w_f}{100} \right)}$ <p>For continuous sheets:</p> $w_f = \min \left\{ 0.9d, h_w \frac{\sin(\theta + \alpha)}{\sin \theta} \right\}, \text{ and } s_f = w_f$
TR55	$V_{Rd,f} = \frac{A_{fw}}{s_f} \left(d_{fv} - \frac{n_{ss}}{3} l_{t,max} \cos \alpha \right) E_{fd} \varepsilon_{fse} \sin \alpha + \cos \alpha$ $n_{ss} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{, fully-wrapped} \\ 1 & \text{, U-wrapped} \end{cases}, l_{t,max} = 0.7 \sqrt{\frac{E_{fd} t_f}{f_{ctk}}}, A_{fw} = 2n t_f w_f$ $\varepsilon_{fse} = \min \left\{ \varepsilon_{fd} / 2, 0.5 \sqrt{\frac{f_{ctk}}{E_{fd} t_f}}, 0.004 \right\}, E_{fd} = \frac{E_{fk}}{\gamma_{FRP,mE}}, \varepsilon_{fd} = \frac{\varepsilon_{fk}}{\gamma_{FRP,mE}}$ <p>For continuous sheets: $w_f = \sin \alpha$, and $s_f = 1$</p> <p>Note: ε_{fse} should be greater than 0.002. if not, this formulation is not applicable.</p>
CIDAR2006	$V_f = 2 f_{fed} t_f \cdot \frac{w_f}{s_f} \cdot h_{fe} \cdot (\cot \theta + \cot \alpha) \cdot \sin \alpha$ $f_{fed} = D_f \cdot f_{fd,max}$ <p>Fully wrapped:</p> $f_{fd,max} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\gamma_f} \cdot \phi_R \cdot f_{fu} ; \varepsilon_f \leq 1.5\% \\ \frac{1}{\gamma_f} \cdot \phi_R \cdot E_f \cdot \varepsilon_f ; \varepsilon_f > 1.5\% \end{cases} ; D_f = 0.5 \left(1 + \frac{z_t}{z_b} \right), L_e = \sqrt{\frac{E_f t_f}{f_{ck}}}$ <p>For U- Wrapped:</p> $D_f = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\pi \cdot \lambda} \cdot \frac{1 - \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \lambda)}{\sin(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \lambda)} ; \lambda = \frac{L_{max}}{L_e} \leq 1 \quad (L_{max} = \frac{h_{fe}}{\sin \alpha}) \\ 1 - \frac{\pi - 2}{\pi \lambda} ; \lambda = \frac{L_{max}}{L_e} > 1 \end{cases}$

	$f_{fd,max} = \min \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\gamma_f} \phi_R \cdot f_{fu} & \beta_L = \begin{cases} \lambda, & \lambda \leq 1 \\ 1, & \lambda > 1 \end{cases} \\ \frac{1}{\gamma_f} \times 0.35 \times \beta_L \times \beta_W \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_f \cdot \sqrt{f_{ck}}}{t_f}} & \beta_w = \sqrt{\frac{2 - w_f / (s_f \cdot \sin \alpha)}{1 + w_f / (s_f \cdot \sin \alpha)}} \end{cases}$ $h_{fe} = z_b - z_t, z_b = 0.9d, z_t = d_{ft}$
<p>Chen et al. (2013) (Only for U-wraps)</p>	$V_f = 2K_{max} E_f \varepsilon_{fe} t_f w_f \frac{h_{f,e} (\cot \theta + \cot \alpha) \sin \alpha}{s_f}$ $\varepsilon_{fe} = \varepsilon_{f,max} D_f; \varepsilon_{f,max} = \min \begin{cases} f_{fu} / E_f \\ \sigma_{db,max} / E_f \end{cases}$ $\sigma_{db,max} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2E_f G_f}{t_f}} & l_{max} \geq l_e \\ \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{l}{l_e}\right) \sqrt{\frac{2E_f G_f}{t_f}} & l_{max} < l_e \end{cases}$ $l_{max} = \frac{h_{f,e} + h_t + h_b}{\sin \alpha}; l_e = \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\delta_f E_f t_f}{\tau_f}}$ $D_f = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \cdot \frac{h_{df}}{h_{f,e}}; h_{df} = 2\delta_f \left(\frac{h_{f,e}}{w_{e,p} \sin(\theta + \alpha)}\right); w_{e,p} = \delta_f \left(\frac{1 + \frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{h_{f,e}}{L_e \sin \alpha} - 1\right)}{\sin(\theta + \alpha)}\right)$ $\delta_f = 2G_f / \tau_f; G_f = 0.308 \beta_w \sqrt{f_t}; \tau_f = 1.5 \beta_w f_t; \beta_w = \sqrt{\frac{2 - w_f / (s_f \sin \alpha)}{1 + w_f / (s_f \sin \alpha)}}; f_t = 0.395 (f'_c / 0.8)^{0.55}$ <p>h_{fe} is effective height of FRP.</p>
<p>Notes: - Unit values for the safety factors and average values for the material properties were adopted in the analysis performed.</p>	